

Enabling Domain Experts to Train Efficient Few-Shot Incremental Landmark Recognition

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Abstract—A web-based application for incremental training of landmark recognition, suitable for domain experts without machine learning expertise is presented. Its backend uses the fine-grained image classification network API-Net in a few-shot setting, making use of the two-stage fine-tuning paradigm. The aim is to enable rapid training of a classifier for recognizing new landmarks in video content, supporting needs in media production. Using base models trained on two different datasets, we demonstrate the speed and effectiveness of the application in training the networks to detect new landmarks. In addition, our application provides the ability to retrain a previously learned landmark with further data, e.g. to improve performance for views or imaging conditions not well supported by the model. This feature ensures that the model remains up-to-date with evolving datasets and environmental conditions, thereby improving its accuracy and adaptability over time.

Index Terms—landmark recognition, incremental training, API-Net, few-shot, demo application

I. INTRODUCTION

Multimedia applications such as XR applications require high-fidelity 3D models, especially for landmarks like buildings or public spaces. Traditionally, obtaining such models was labor-intensive, often involving drone-based aerial imaging. However, utilizing vast archives of image and video data from broadcasters and cultural institutions provides an alternative. Although video data often lacks precise temporal annotations, its multiple views of landmarks under similar conditions are valuable for 3D reconstruction. In order to recognise landmarks in these videos, in one of our previous works [1] we developed methods for training a landmark classifier based on API-Net [2], a fine-grained classifier network for a few-shot scenario. In addition, in a follow-up work [3] we investigated how this approach can be used for incremental training of landmark recognition.

In order to put the training process into the hands of users, we propose a web-based application tailored for incremental training of a landmark recognition model. The primary objective is to enable domain experts, who need to add support for a specific landmark to an existing classifier, to perform the training in an interactive way using a few sets of weakly annotated examples. By using two different datasets to train

network models, we demonstrate the speed and effectiveness of the application in learning to recognise new landmarks. Furthermore, our application allows users to retrain individual landmarks, ensuring its adaptability to evolving datasets and environmental conditions. The interactive applications allows experimenting with different parameter sets.

The rest of the paper is structured as follows: In Section II, we discuss related work in the field of incremental learning and about available frameworks for testing. The used approach for incremental training is summarized in Section III. In Section IV, we describe our web application for class-incremental landmark training. Finally, in Section V, we conclude the paper and discuss future work.

II. RELATED WORK

Class-incremental learning enables the gradual assimilation of knowledge from new classes, enriching the classifier’s capability to encompass a wide array of classes. However, directly incorporating instances from new classes often triggers catastrophic forgetting, leading to a notable decline in performance. Gido et al. [4] offer a comprehensive overview of incremental learning strategies, categorizing them into four main types: parameter regularization, functional regularization, replay, and template-based classification. Among these, replay methods have demonstrated superior performance in classification scenarios, as highlighted by Gido et al.’s evaluation on the MNIST and CIFAR-100 datasets.

Zhou et al. [5] further categorized methods for addressing class-incremental learning (CIL) into three groups: data-centric, model-centric, and algorithm-centric approaches. Data-centric techniques focus on managing CIL through exemplars, which can be achieved via data replay or data regularization. Model-centric methods aim to prevent model parameters from drifting or enhance the network structure to improve representability. Finally, algorithm-centric methods employ knowledge distillation to mitigate forgetting or address biases within the CIL model.

Several techniques are commonly employed and combined within various methods. Knowledge distillation involves training a student model with both base and novel classes to mimic the performance of a teacher model trained only on base classes [6], [7]. Model rectification addresses differences in

the value range of predicted logits between base and novel classes, often due to sample imbalances, by adding a bias correction layer [8]. Exemplar selection strategies such as herding [9] or diversity maximization are applied to retain base class training data, while feature space storage reduces memory requirements by saving extracted feature vectors [8]. Techniques such as REMIND [10] use frozen layers to obtain tensor representations, which are then quantized and stored for future replay, allowing efficient retention of old training instances.

Several open source projects and libraries illustrate the concept of incremental or continuous learning. For example, Avalanche [11] is an end-to-end library for continuous learning based on PyTorch providing benchmarks and state-of-the-art continuous learning algorithms. Sequoia [12], is a flexible research framework that aims to make research in continuous learning more reproducible, accessible and interpretable. It is also based on PyTorch. In addition, Renate [13] is a Python package designed for automatic retraining of neural network models, with a framework for hyper-parameter optimisation.

Most of these libraries focus on providing the tools and frameworks to implement and evaluate continual learning models, focusing on a developer user group. They typically include benchmark datasets and tasks, but they usually do not provide ready-to-use applications suitable for domain experts.

III. APPROACH FOR INCREMENTAL TRAINING

The proposed web application is based on our approach for incremental training based on Swin+API-Net [3]. Starting from a network, which is pretrained for the base classes, the incremental training process involves three main steps:

- 1) Training of novel classes: The classification layer of the Swin+API-Net is trained only for the novel classes/landmarks and a *None* class using the backbone network of the model trained for the base landmarks. This ensures that the backbone does not need to be adapted (features can be reused).
- 2) Join network: To create a network that can classify both the base and the new landmarks, the two networks are merged. This is done by using the same backbone network and joining the classification layers of the two models.
- 3) Fine-tuning: The resulting network is fine-tuned by retraining it with the same number of images for each landmark.

The landmark classes are trained against a *None* class in order to handle images that do not belong to any of the landmarks. The approach uses the replay concept, where examples of the base classes are stored for training. To limit memory and computational requirements, only a maximum of 10 randomly selected examples are used for the base classes. We freeze the backbone for training because we are starting from a model that is already trained on more than 100 landmarks. Therefore, only the features of the base classes extracted using the backbone need to be stored. For new landmarks, as many examples as available are used. This

Fig. 1. Incremental training: First, the landmark recognition network (Swin+API-Net) was trained to distinguish between one or more novel landmarks and other image content (*None* class). Then the part of the classification layer for the novel landmarks (not the noise part) is copied and joined to the classification layer of the original network. Finally, the obtained network is trained with a balanced set of landmark images and a set of *None* class images.

can lead to certain landmarks being given a higher weight during recognition. To balance this, a bias correction layer can optionally be added after the classification layer in the fine tuning step. Other options for training novel classes are to use base class examples marked as *None* Class and creating a balanced training dataset (equal number of *None* Class images) by data augmentation (cropping, resizing, flipping).

IV. TRAINING WEB APPLICATION

The usage scenario of the training application involves acquiring training data for a specific landmark in a first step. In a semi-automatic way, these images should be filtered to use only images showing the landmark in different views. After that, various settings can be made before starting the incremental training. If the landmark has been trained before, the corresponding part of the classification layer will be replaced by the newly trained one in the join network step (see Section III). To test the result, an arbitrary video can be selected and analysed. Afterwards, the video frames in which a landmark has been recognized and their time stamps are displayed. The user can choose between two pretrained base models. One model is trained on a dataset from the Italian public broadcaster RAI, which includes monuments of Italy [14] (163 landmarks). The other one is trained on the Weakly Annotated Video Landmark (WAVL) dataset (141 landmarks), which is available to the research community¹.

We have implemented it as a client-server application in Python by using the gradio package [15]. The web user interface is shown in Figure 2.

¹<https://github.com/XRecoEU/WAVL-Dataset>

Fig. 2. Screenshot of the web application for incremental training of landmarks.

The first step is to select the base model (trained on the WAVL or RAI datasets) to which we want to add a new landmark. This can be done using the “Dataset” drop down menu on the right hand side of the user interface.

To obtain training images of a landmark, we integrate two web search engines (see top left of the web user interface 2). The first one uses the image search functionality of DuckDuckGo². The second is a metasearch service implemented in the XReco project [16], which adapts and connects several search engines and repositories, including public repositories such as WikiMedia Commons as well as public content feeds from broadcasters like Deutsche Welle. The search term for the landmark and the landmark name can be different. Additional images can be found by using different or extended search terms. All images found during the web search will be displayed. Images which don’t show the landmark can be manually rejected simply by clicking.

Since the aim is to use weakly labelled video as an image source, the Swin+API-Net network [1] includes a semantic image segmentation network (SWIN transformer network) to filter out images that do not contain buildings. In the demo application, we separate the image filtering process from the

training process with API-Net. The filtering with the Swin Transformer Network can be initiated manually using the “Filter Image” button. For incremental training with API-Net the following settings can be selected:

- *Inc Train All*: Base class examples marked as *None* class are also used for training of novel classes.
- *Bias Correction*: For the novel landmarks a bias correction layer is added after the classification layer in the fine tuning step.
- *Balanced Inc train*: Image examples of the novel landmarks are extended by data augmentation, in order to get a balanced dataset between novel and *None* class examples.

After pressing the “Start Training” button, incremental training takes approx. 60-80 seconds (measured using an NVIDIA GeForce RTX 3090), depending on the number of novel images to be trained. Once the process is finished the novel landmark appears in the landmark list (drop-down menu on the right with the label “Landmarks”).

A video can be uploaded via the video view for testing. Once the recognition process has been started using the “Recognize Landmark” button, one frame per second of the video is analysed.

The recognition scores of identified landmarks are tracked

²<https://duckduckgo.com/>

and combined across the video sequence, providing a quantitative measure of the significance of each landmark. The landmark with the highest cumulative score and where the maximum score is higher or equal the recognition threshold becomes the focus of further analysis. It undergoes another round of clustering, whereby the frames in which it was recognized with the highest scores are selected and displayed with their relative video time position in the lower window on the right-hand side of the interface.

V. CONCLUSIONS

In this work, we present a web-based application in order to enable domain experts to incrementally train a few-shot landmark recognition method. Using the fine-grained image classification network API-Net in a few-shot setting, our application facilitates the rapid integration of novel landmarks into an existing classifier. By providing two different datasets for model training, we demonstrate the efficiency and effectiveness of the application to learn the detection of new landmarks from a limited number of examples. Furthermore, the ability to retrain the network for individual landmarks ensures its adaptability to evolving datasets and environmental conditions, thereby increasing its accuracy and flexibility over time. The interactive nature of our application provides users with the flexibility to experiment with different parameter settings, further refining the performance of the trained models.

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